

Effect of planting date on grain yield of cultivar Morelos A92 and breeding line CAEZ401. Zacatepec, Morelos, Mexico. 1993.

Filled grains panicle⁻¹ and grain weight were the most affected by late transplanting. For the two genotypes, filled grains panicle⁻¹ went down from 63 in the first date to 47 in the last date while 1,000 grain weight was reduced from 43.6 to 40.7 g.

The regression equations obtained and the parameters used to evaluate fitness of the models in each period are shown in the table. Within each period, the best fit was obtained when GR and MMT were

evaluated together (model 4), except in the period f+20, when MMT and MMT2 (model 2) were comparable. The fitness of model 4 was higher for f-20 and f+20 than their combination.

These results show that variation in incident global radiation and mean minimum temperature during the period 20 d before or 20 d after flowering may explain much of the variation in grain yield in the different planting dates for irrigated rice. ■

Integrated pest management—diseases

Effects of neem derivatives on sheath rot in scented rice

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We assessed the efficacy of botanical biocides and pesticides (fungicides carbendazim and mancozeb) for controlling sheath rot (ShR) of scented rice. Leaf extract and fungicides were applied twice as foliar sprays at a 2-wk interval beginning at booting. The field trial was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications using scented hybrid rice JJ92. Plot size was 5 × 2 m.

ShR incidence was measured as the percentage of infected tillers in 25

Comparison of biocides to control sheath rot incidence and grain yield of scented rice JJ92.

Treatment	Percent ShR incidence ^a	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)
Neem oil (3%)	30.22 (33.25)	5.2
Neem seed kernel extract (5%)	26.30 (29.70)	5.0
Monocrotophos (1250 ml ha ⁻¹)	25.86 (30.48)	4.4
Carbendazim (500 g ha ⁻¹)	24.27 (29.80)	4.1
Mancozeb (1 kg ha ⁻¹)	30.47 (33.38)	3.4
Monocrotophos (1250 ml) + carbendazim (500 g ha ⁻¹)	27.57 (31.61)	3.8
Monocrotophos (1250 ml) + mancozeb (1 kg ha ⁻¹)	22.87 (28.49)	4.5
Nochi (10%) (<i>Vitex negundo</i>)	26.80 (31.10)	4.2
Untreated check	37.52 (37.67)	3.2
LSD (P=0.05)	1.10	.5

^aMeans of three replications. Data in parentheses are arcsine-transformed values.

randomly selected hills/plot 20 d after the last spray. Higher yields were recorded with neem oil (3%), neem seed kernel extract (5%), and monocrotophos (1,250 ml ha⁻¹) + mancozeb (1 kg ha⁻¹). Standard fungicides carbendazim (500 g ha⁻¹) and monocrotophos (1,250 ml ha⁻¹), and

mancozeb (1 kg ha⁻¹) effectively reduced ShR incidence (see table).

Using a spray of neem seed kernel extract generated higher grain yield and effectively reduced disease incidence, although to a lesser degree, than using regular fungicides. ■

Seed borne nature and seed transmission of rice sheath blight

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Although rice sheath blight (ShB) caused by *Rhizoctonia solani* is documented as a seedborne disease, evidence of this nature is lacking. We investigated spotted and apparently healthy seeds of rice cultivar Swarna Mashuri to find out the mode of transmission involved. The seeds were collected from a heavily ShB-infected rice crop from the BCKV Regional Research Farm.

Effect of *R. solani* infection on rice germination and seed health. West Bengal^a, India.

Treatment	Seeds yielding <i>R. solani</i> (%)	Germination (%)	Seedling infection (%)	Seedling collapse (%)	Shoot fresh weight (mg)	Shoot dry weight (mg)	Root fresh weight (mg)	Root dry weight (mg)
Naturally Infested seeds	37.83	59.09	14.88	4.35	279.46	46.83	485.7	64.1
Artificially inoculated seeds	56.35	70.66	23.58	9.21	361.20	66.05	673.75	120.13
Apparently healthy seeds	12.17	73.19	0	0	467.26	94.3	922.4	174.3
SE ±	0.682	0.655	0.728	0.127	0.57	0.376	0.575	0.324
LSD (0.05)	1.520	1.459	1.624	0.284	1.286	0.838	1.281	0.721
Unsterilized seeds	50.92	65.63	8.70	9.09	334.66	60.52	608.66	109
Surface-sterilized seeds	19.98	69.67	6.93	0	403.94	77.60	779.23	130.02
SE ±	0.545	0.535	0.594	0.018	0.47	0.307	0.469	0.265
LSD (0.05)	1.214	1.19	1.326	0.024	1.050	0.684	1.04	0.590
Interaction								
SE ±	0.9315	0.9266	1.03	0.032	0.81	0.532	0.813	0.459
LSD (0.05)	2.07	2.06	2.29	0.072	1.819	1.85	1.81	1.022

^aAll percentage data are transformed angular values.

Healthy seeds (200 g) were placed in a sterilized erlenmeyer flask and 10 cm of air-dried inoculum of *R. solani* (grown in sand-maize-meal medium for 15 d at 20 °C) was added to it. The flask was shaken for 5 min.

R. solani was isolated from spotted, artificially inoculated, and apparently healthy seeds. The seeds were placed in 2% sterilized water agar in petri dishes and incubated at 28 °C for 72 h. One lot was seeded without surface sterilization; the other lot was seeded after surface sterilization with NaOCl solution for 1 min.

Among naturally infected seeds (spotted), 40% of unsterilized seeds and 36% of surface-sterilized seeds yielded *R. solani* (see table). This indicates that in naturally infested seeds, the fungus was both externally and internally seedborne. The data for artificially inoculated and apparently healthy seeds were 100 and 15, and 17 and 0, respectively. Isolation of the fungus from some unsterilized apparently healthy seeds is probably due to surface contamination. None of the apparently healthy seeds showed seedling infection. Seedling infection was higher in artificially

inoculated unsterilized seeds. Surface sterilization resulted in reduced seedling infection, indicating that the fungus in artificially inoculated seeds was externally borne.

Infection of seedlings grown from *R. solani*-infested seeds had considerable effect on seedling health. This was indicated by the much higher fresh and dry weight of the seedlings grown from healthy seeds as compared with those from naturally infected seeds (both unsterilized and surface-sterilized) and artificially inoculated unsterilized ones. ■

Serological evidence for inducing resistance to rice tungro viruses using antiviral principles

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Use of antiviral principles (AVPs) from plant sources is found to reduce rice tungro virus (RTV) infection. We conducted a study to obtain serological evidence for the effectiveness of AVP application in managing rice tungro disease.

AVPs from seed sprouts of pigeonpea (PP-AVP) and mungbean (MB-AVP) were sprayed at 10% concentration on rice variety Co 43. The following day, each plant was inoculated with two viruliferous *Nephotettix virescens* (Distant). Twenty-five plants were inoculated in each treatment; inoculated plants without AVP application served as the control. Leaf samples were collected 25 d after inoculation and tested using enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) to determine the presence of rice tungro bacilliform (RTBV) and rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV).

The RTV antigen was optimally diluted in carbonate-bicarbonate buffer (pH 9.6), coated at 100 µl well⁻¹ of ELISA plate and incubated overnight at 4 °C. The plate was washed three times with PBS Tween 20 (PBS-T). Bovine serum albumin (2%) was added to block nonspecific reaction and the

Detection by indirect ELISA of rice tungro-associated viruses in rice plants following AVP application and RTBV and RTSV inoculation. Coimbatore, India.^a

Treatment	Plants infected (no.)/plants inoculated (no.)	Absorbance at 405 nm			
		RTSV		RTBV	
		Infected	Uninfected	Infected	Uninfected
RTV-inoculated (control)	24/25	1.111-1.525	0.060	1.200-1.600	-0.025
AVP-treated and RTV-inoculated					
10% Pigeonpea AVP	4/25	0.860-0.939	0.069-0.125	0.831-0.945	0.068-0.120
10% Mungbean AVP	5/25	0.550-0.925	0.070-0.090	0.745-0.940	0.070-0.085
Healthy (ELISA check)		-	0.070-0.152	-	0.075-0.150

^aRTV = rice tungro virus, AVP = antiviral principles, ELISA = enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay, RTSV = rice tungro spherical virus, RTBV = rice tungro bacilliform virus.

plate was washed with PBS-T. The rabbit I_gG antiserum specific to RTBV and RTSV was diluted 1:100 with PBS-T buffer and incubated for 90 min at 37 °C, then washed three times with PBS-T. The alkaline phosphatase conjugated goat antirabbit was diluted 1:7,000, placed in the well, and incubated for 1 h at 37 °C. The plate was then washed five times with PBS-T.

Freshly prepared substrate solution containing P-nitrophenyl phosphate (PNP) (1 mg ml⁻¹ in 10% diethanolamine buffer) was added and incubated at room temperature for 1 h. The reaction was stopped with 3 M NaOH. Absorbance at 405 nm was recorded using the ELISA reader. Absorbance values greater than 0.152 (maximum value for healthy plants) indicate a positive reaction. The ELISA test was repeated.

Application of PP-AVP and MB-AVP reduced virus infection to 16 and 20%,

respectively (untreated control has 96% infection). RTBV and RTSV could not be detected in plants that did not show any visible symptoms, indicating their absence in AVP-treated plants. But the presence of RTSV and RTBV was detected by ELISA in all plants showing infection symptoms.

Applying PP-AVP protected the plants from both RTSV and RTBV infection, shown by the reduced percentage of infection in AVP-treated plants. The concentration of both viruses was reduced in AVP-treated plants, even though they are infected by the viruses, indicating that AVPs may interfere with the replication of rice tungro-associated viruses (see table). The AVPs do not appear to have any effect on leafhopper feeding.

Studies on the characterization of AVPs and molecular biology of resistance induced by AVPs in rice are in progress. ■